

θ -Calculi

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Abstract

For two Kolmogorov spaces and a split map $\mathcal{K}$ between the two, the twisted portion of the di-morphism is regular up to a certain convergent point θ . Topologically, this is an accumulation point. Abstractly, this is the co-fibration of a spectral compass. We will discuss here the Goodwillie calculus and forcing notions for motivic Kolmogorov spaces.

0. Preamble

For two differentiable schemes, one always has a pair of profinite morphisms to and from each. We define $\mathfrak{D}_{\text{CENT}}$ to be both the source and target of each of these “excision functors.”¹ We depart from our reference here in that we are *most interested* in working, not with polynomials $\mathcal{P}$, but with (rings of) *formal power series*, $\mathcal{P}_{\mathbb{F}}$. For each of these series, we define a natural extension $\mathcal{P}_{F_{\text{ext}}}$, which is stable under all of the sorts of pullbacks one would expect a conservative extension to be faithful to. In our notation, we will mostly sidestep the property of extensiveness by denoting a regular ring with extension as either R or $\mathcal{P}_{\mathbb{F}}$. We do not “require” our rings to be extensible, *per sé*, although it would be a lot nicer for us if they were.

This is because, for maps into integral domains $R \rightarrow I$, there is always at least *one* surjection onto a cardinal $\mathfrak{o}$, and we’d like (as often as possible) for this surjection to be a genuine bijection. We go, flexibly, from talking about *neighborhoods* (and the sobriety of neighborhoods, as spaces), to talking about density functors on some interval. We’d like to consider the interval as an *extension* over any of the elements it includes, which can be represented as spaces which are *homothetic* to the interval under a gauge or scaling factor. To move between numbers on this line, we operate using “trivial”² twist consisting of two non-trivial half-twists, t and t' . In some important sense, intervals most closely approximate the traditional calculus; in fact, the common Lebesgue integration is merely the *shape functor* taken over some covering space.

Mathematicians have often sought greener pastures – newer soils, which were ripe for their genetically modified seed; *cohesive homotopy theory* was, by some, seen as the new means by which we would come to understand spaces (abstractly) and the various *functors* they admitted simply by their

¹ See [Haine], proposition 2.10

² In the sense that they do not uniquely determine the torsion class of their projectors

presence! Really, it is quite simple. We generalize a bit here, and so this segment should be considered somewhat nonstandard.

One picks a few “modalities”, namely, $\vdash, \dashv, \#$, and $\flat$. One then picks from a number of “things” symbols; e.g., $\sqsupset, \lambda, \Gamma$. Then, one establishes the autonomous existence of a number of symbolic relationships between these “things” by means of inductive reasoning. We represent co-adjointness and duality through the hom-sets of “things,” which correspond to functors of modalities.

0.1 Stably Flat Functors

Let $\sqsupset^\#$ be a pure module with weight k . Let $\bar{k}$ be a summation of co-weights. Then, a *stably flat functor* is an exact, faithful functor $\Gamma^\flat \rightarrow \sqsupset^\#$ so that co-cycles of $\sqsupset$ are preserved from the pre-image. Let us call some special *frame* in these co-cycles φ .

Then, one has, by taking $\varphi^{-1}\Gamma^\flat_{\text{CO}}$, an n -topos, n which is currently unknown to us, but which is required in order to do computations involving the truncation or forgetfulness of an isotonic chain. Notice that a stably flat functor has to be projective on objects, since

$$\text{proj}(\Gamma^\flat) = \text{coker}(\sqsupset)_\varphi$$

Also, since we want to preserve inverse co-limits, we require that there is at least one effective pullback to a quasi-coherent descent potential.

Definition 0.1.1 Let $\mathbf{f}(k)$ be any function. Let $\mathbf{mRk}$ be a relationship between m and k , which is non-trivial. Then there is a non-trivial *gap* in the *image* of the function. If this gap decays homothetically³, then we call the difference (in **Sets**) $m \setminus k$, the *descent potential*.

Remark For two perfect fields, $\kappa, \kappa', \kappa' \setminus \kappa = \{m, k\}_{\text{MOD}}$ is a valid descent potential, assuming there is a site-level equivalence between the representations of κ, κ' . This is a stronger requirement than extensibility for rings.

We tacitly relate the set-theoretic summation

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [0, n) = \gamma$$

with a p -ary integration

$$\int_0^{\infty} n = \infty$$

by means of a *compass*, Ω_X^Y , which takes as its input *pseudo-harmonic* functions, and outputs simplices of a complex $\tilde{D}$.

We say the relationship between $\text{ev}(\gamma)$ and $\text{coev}(\infty)$ is sufficient enough for us to impose a (γ, ∞) -display over a section of the *stack* encompassed by Ω_X^Y , so we have

³ To generalize the linear case to the linear-symmetric case

$$\Omega_X^Y \phi_{\gamma, \infty} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{Eff}}$$

and the effective action is mediated by these two parameters. By composition of terms, we form a *new compass*, $\Omega_{X, \gamma}^{Y, \infty}$, and we have license to speak of a *complex space* as a sort of spectral ∞ -groupoid.

Essentially though, this is a *combinatorial* structure, although as such it is deceptively smooth.

0.2 Witnesses of effective action

Let $\mathbb{A}$ be a genuine $\mathbb{A}_\infty$ -ring, and let $E: \mathbb{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{A}$ be a homomorphism of compasses. Then, we say that a *witness* to the display block, which is homothetic to $\mathbf{A}_{\text{Eff}}$, is a *holonomic* potential-valued object p . By virtue of the transport provided to p by the motivic cycle conditions obeyed by $\mathbb{A}$ -schemes, we have at least one inertial frame, $\bar{q}$, which corresponds to an action of p . By an action of p , we mean a sum of constants in the field $\mathbb{Q}/p$. We, in other words (see, [Haine], pg. 8), mean that $\bar{q}$ is a p -homogenous group of actions.

Fig. 1

Chains of varying periodicity are related via co-dimension to their higher-order analogues. They are related, via displays, to other chains which sit inside the same “chain cycle” group.

$b_3 \rightarrow c_4$ defines a degenerate action of nodal singularities.⁴ Here, we define the “chain cycle” rules for c_n to be a map $n \rightarrow n^+$, where n^+ is the “successor” (mod r) function. b_3 acts perversely by transcendence over c_4 by splitting its map to b_6 . It acts normally to access a_3 via “equivalence” of subobject identifier (here a subscript).

⁴ See [Kelevator, 2.11]

§1 Relationships that act via co-cycles

Let $x\mathbf{R}y$ be a relationship between x and y . Let $\tilde{R}$ denote the monodromy of $x \sqcup y$. Let $x \rightarrow y$ be a pre-transitive function, so that $\text{proj}(y) \simeq f \circ g(x)$ is onto. Let $\text{proj}(y)$ be split. Then, there is an inner hom,

$$\text{hom}(\text{proj}(y)) \cup g(x) = \mathbf{H}$$

so that the functor g can act by torsion on $\mathbf{H}$.

This gives

$$\text{Fun}(\mathbf{H}, \mathbf{H})$$

an automorphic resolution at some designated pole p . If $p \rightarrow p$ is constant, and stable over injections, then the compass homomorphism $\mathbf{H} \rightarrow \mathbf{H}$ is canonically filtered by the split functor f^2 . Finally, we have a stably flat target object, $\mathbf{z}^{=1/2} \text{proj}(y)$.

$$\sum_{y=k}^{k+d^{-1}} p = \mathbf{R}_k$$

We denote by $\mathbf{R}_k$ a rough measure of the projective “strength” of a relationship, which we obtain by measuring the differences in radii of open balls in each slice of $\mathbf{H}$. If two open balls, b_1 and b_2 share the same loop group, write $\mathbf{LG}(\mathbf{B})$. We then measure the time-correlated potential evolution of $\mathbf{LG}(\mathbf{B})$ to obtain

$$\mathbf{LG}(\mathbf{B}) \cup \sum_{\tau=0}^{\infty} \partial\tau,$$

where the right-hand side has opfibrations to perfect sets.

Proposition 1.0.1 Let $\mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ be stably flat. Let $\mathcal{X} \rightrightarrows \mathcal{X}$ be stably flat on either the top or bottom cell. Then, there is a θ -link, Σ , which conserves polarity, mod -1^n .

Proof

We see that there is always at least *one* stably flat morphism $-1^n \mathcal{X}$.

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} \mathcal{X} & \longrightarrow & \mathcal{X} & \xrightleftharpoons{\text{stab}} & \mathcal{X} \\ & & \downarrow & & \\ & & -1^n & & \\ & & \downarrow & & \\ \mathcal{X} & \longrightarrow & \mathcal{X} & \xrightleftharpoons{\text{stab}} & \mathcal{X} \end{array}$$

So, we have $\text{cofib}(\mathcal{X}) := f^2: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$, which descends to a split stably flat morphism.

Remark This is a effectively a spin chain of period $\mathbb{Z}/2$.

§1.1 Cocycle Inclusions

Let $C \rightarrow C$ be a map of cocycles $c\mu_0, \dots, c\mu_n$. Write $[0:(n)]$ for the series of path-connected time-step evolutions which move a system towards a point $\mathcal{W} \sum_{k=0}^n \mu_k$.

Let $\mathbf{m}$ be a miniscule co-character of μ_k . If the Shimura datum about $\mathbf{m}$ “plays nicely” with the selected compass, then there should be a correspondence $\text{cor}(\mathbf{m}) = \partial k$. So, if $\mathcal{F}$ is a map of topological classifying stacks, then there is a k -rational torsion point θ to which the timestep evolution of the system converges. We select some interval, $\mathbf{S}$, so that $\theta:\mathbf{S}$ gives an *inner (hom) extension*, and if $\mathbf{F}$ is a stable, reductive field, then there is a display $\phi_\theta:\mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}$ which classifies all functions of θ up to automorphism.

Technically, by a display, here we mean a *geodesic lamination*, because quite simply, a geodesic lamination is produced by a covering set of displays. We note that the transforming geometries of space are associated with the appropriate *deck transformations*.

Definition 1.1.1 If $\mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}$ is a map of clopen spaces, then we say it is a *short trip*.

This definition is motivated by the works of, e.g. Girard on proof nets. A short trip is an automatic cocycle inclusion which uses no forcing notion, and so is not transcendental, and so is algebraically reducible to $\mathbb{Q}/p$. A short trip is a period-preserving (and hence, trace preserving) map between topoi which is also the trivial one-fold covering.

§1.2 Opfibrations

Let $\mathbf{S}(\mathcal{D})$ be a *short trip*. Then, there is the “natural” fibration $\mathcal{D} \rightarrow_s \mathcal{D}$, which is a Hurewicz isomorphism, and then there is the associated opfibration, $\mathcal{D} \rightarrow^s \mathcal{D}$. Assume that short trips are always inclusions of cocycles. Then, there is a natural bijection $\mathbf{S}(\mathcal{D}) \leftrightarrow \mathcal{D}$, so that the fibers acted upon by half-twists are one-to-one with a D_p -brane.

Let $\pi_k(\mathcal{X})$ be some gauge-invariant transformation of a homotopy object. We characterize this shape in terms of its *diagonal group*, which generates a hyperplane $\not\perp$ that perfectly divides a polar space into neighborhoods of equivalences mod p . We have worked with the operations of holonomy and homothety, so now we provide a succinct formalization:

- Holonomy: $\nabla \Lambda \rightrightarrows \Lambda_{ij}^\delta \in \text{rep}(\mathbf{H})$
- Homothety: $\{\Omega_x^y \Rightarrow \tilde{\Omega}_x^y | x, y = \{\{x,y\}/p\}\}$

Holonomy is to homothety as electricity is to magnetism. A homothetic connection admitting a short trip is a fairly good model for the transport of current. We have

$$\Omega_{i,x}^{j,y}(\delta) = \nabla_k^{j-i} \omega$$

where equality is the Christoffel connection. This gives us a “stable”⁵ test bed for our equations in $2k+1$ -dimensions; $k < 3$. We obtain the $k=3$ case by extending *cocycle inclusion* from

$$\begin{aligned} \bullet &\rightarrow \tilde{\bullet} \\ &\text{to} \\ \bullet &\rightrightarrows \tilde{\bullet} \end{aligned}$$

where each black dot represents a stable test geometry. Subscripts indicate subobject identification at an arbitrary locus; for our purposes, we prefer it to be real. Let

$$K \rightrightarrows \tilde{K}_H$$

be a split monomorphism between Kähler spaces, with the second Hermitian. We can write $H_\delta \rightarrow K_{\tau > 0}$ for the associated $\mathbf{K}$ -map of Kolmogorov spaces.

Figure 2

$stab \circ \mathcal{K}$ yields the canonical descent from $T_{\mathbb{ZAR}}(\mathbf{K})$ to $K_{\epsilon t}$

We see, we have effectively two ways of generating the space $K_{\tau > 0}$, and one of these ways gives us two objects for the price of one. So, $\text{Hom}(K, K_{\tau > 0})$ is certainly “bigger” than $\text{Hom}(H_\delta, K_{\tau > 0})$. So, we see there is no isomorphism $H_\delta = K$ due to detachment of H_δ . The functor $\mathcal{K}$ essentially equips K with a subobject identifier H which is compatible with the subject identifier δ on our object H . We realize this as a “short trip” from K to K_H .

Proposition 1.2.1 The op-fibration $K_{\tau > 0} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow K$ is a short trip.

Proof Since $\tau > 0$, any opfibration $K_{\tau > 0} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow K$ will have a $(\tau > 0)^{-1}$ propagation time. Thus, the trip is relatively shorter than $K_{\tau > 0} \rightarrow H_\delta$, which is 1.

⁵ Faithfully flat

$$\tilde{R}(\mathbb{K}) < \tilde{R}^{Fin+}$$

§1.3 More remarks on short trips

For an n-exciseive functor

$$K_n: \bar{k} \rightarrow K^{op}$$

We let $K_n \times K_{n-1}$ determine a *loop co-cycle*, and when $\bar{k}$ admits an open Prüffer extension, then the restriction

$$n \twoheadrightarrow n-1 \simeq \text{Fun}(n^\pm)$$

Proposition 1.3.1 When $n^\pm$ is both initial and final, then there is a constant loop action stabilizing n at a point.

$$\mathbf{LG}(N) \rightsquigarrow n$$

We have the partial flag

$$n \subset n^\pm$$

so that the polarity of the point is determined for transitions of displays. So, for a slice $P_{n^\pm}$ of $\mathbb{A}$, and for an orientable cover $\mathcal{Cov}(n)$, we have a smooth holonomy of displays $\Phi_n: \mu_0 \rightarrow \mu_k$.

Proposition 1.3.2 Two actions $a\phi_n, b\phi_m$ which are right-spectral decomposable, admit finite adjunctions into the category of commutative ring spectra.

Proof Let P be a product determining a loop co-cycle. Then, we find, by immersing

$$P \in \text{Grp} \supset \text{RngSp}$$

that the restriction to commutative ring spectra is product-preserving.

§2 θ -convergence

Let $\mathcal{Cov}(X)$ be the covering of a space X by rays γ_m .

$$\gamma_m^{-1} \mathbb{B} \otimes \text{Hom}(X, X) = \text{Spec}(Y)$$

Let $\text{Spec}(Y)$ have n points which are extremely disconnected. Then, for each point, let there be a finite open cover containing the singleton set associated with said point but no other sets. Let there a space $\mathcal{G}$ which is tiled by such neighborhoods. Then, we have a correspondence

$$\mathcal{G}_{\text{FIN}} = \sum_{\rho_n} \simeq \text{Spec}(Y)$$

Banach's fixed point theorem tells us that a map $\mathcal{G} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}_{\text{FIN}}$ should preserve at least *some* fixed point,

$f(x) = \sum_{\rho_n} |_{\rho_n}$. Here, we are interested in thinking about the n-digital restriction as a *focusing* of rays about a

locus ϱ_n with real representation n.

Abusively, we label the map $\varrho_n \rightarrow n$ as a *single object*, θ . For a trivial bundle $\mathcal{I}$, the map $\text{Spec}(Y\mathcal{I}) \rightarrow \text{Spec}(Y)$ is *trace preserving*, because it preserves θ . For sets in **DispSets**, there is a unique character $\{*\}$ which is the fixed fibered limit for any k-form derivative. We call open sets whose displays “point” towards this character θ -convergent.

Proposition 2.0.1 $\mathcal{C}ov(X)$ is θ -convergent.

Proof Since, for every Newton polygon in $\mathcal{C}ov(X)$, there is a finite set of deformations which one can apply in order to make $\text{Spec}(Y)$ agree up to $*$ -filtered colimits with $\lambda_{CUR} \mathcal{C}ov(X)$.

Therefore, for every finite combination of edges and vertices, there is at least one Urysohn point which resides in a locally perfect space.

For two spaces of finite presentation, the set of bijective automorphisms between them is foliated⁶ by a collection of fibrations between a θ -convergent series and some “crystalline” structure, Q . For instance, a set of vectors may be modeled as an *isocrystal* whose generator is some real lie group L . Pointwise additive functions (scalars) of such an isocrystal may be used to “transport”⁷ a set of variables using equivalence relations “inside” of the crystal itself. So, the price we pay for our line of thinking is that we now require, for most formulations, a new derivation of fusion rules in many distinct contexts.

Definition 2.1.0 Let $\mathcal{A}$ and $\mathcal{B}$ be stable, additive bicategories. A *fusion rule*, $\mathcal{A} \star \mathcal{B}$, is a distinct *homotopy equivalence* $x=y$ of tensor-objects in $\pi_1 \text{Hom}(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B})$.

For the Goodwillie calculus, or the sequent calculus, we may like a rule like

§2.1.1 Pointwise specification: $\mathcal{A}(a) \star \mathcal{B}(b) \{a\mathbf{R}b | \mathbf{R} \equiv \rightarrow \hat{\epsilon}\}$

For two pro-objects a and b , there is a quick and easy specialization on objects which makes these variables readily accessible. Particularly, this is the $\hat{\epsilon}$ -specialization, which is obtained by taking the smooth symmetric difference between two differentiable stacks.

$$\text{Hom}(\mathcal{A}(a_i) \star \mathcal{B}(b_j)) \simeq \mathbb{M}_{St}^{Top} \circ \mathcal{F}_1$$

Let $\mathbb{E}$ be a regular Euclidean space with a flat metric. Let $\mathbb{H}$ be a >3 -dimensional holomorphic space. Let μ, ν be sub-object identifiers, so that there is a display

$$\phi_d: \mathbb{E}_\mu \rightarrow \mathbb{H}_\nu$$

which admits a short trip to a block $\mathbf{B}$. Then, there is a short trip (of schemes) $P: \mathbb{E} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$. We envision $\mathbf{B}$ as a sort of split-fibered product $\mathbf{B} \Leftarrow \phi_d \times \phi_d$. Assuming each ϕ_d to be decomposable into one projective space, and an affine space, we have that $\mathbf{B}$ forms an analytic variety in the tower $\mathfrak{T}$, where every fibration $\mathfrak{T} \rightarrow \phi_d$ is a rank-one isomorphism.

Definition 2.1.2 A rank n isomorphism is a coherent k-digital cover of cells in a small and full subcategory of an algebraic category.

⁶ Covered, cut out, approximated by

⁷ Transform

Proposition 2.1.3 An edge, R , between two vertices θ and y , is reducible to a rank 1 isomorphism.

Proof We have that θ is our modulus center; so, it precisely parameterizes the smoothest line from y . Therefore, for any pair of objects, θ, y , we form a neighborhood with y on the boundary, and there is a flat curve between the two.

Definition 2.1.4 A *Koszul connection*⁸ is a rank 1 isomorphism $R:\theta \leftrightarrow y$

Remark The proof of Prop. 2.1.3. implies the existence of *Koszul connections* for *any* manifold with *connection*.

A θ -convergent object is one whose pushout $\mathcal{C}ov(X) \rightarrow x \in X$ is *strictly decreasing* with respect to the distance $d(x, \theta)$. This property is dependent upon one or more time-valued parameters. So, we introduce the equation

$$\tau(x) = \lim_{t_0 \rightarrow k} d(x, \theta)$$

Assuming a constant Koszul connection is maintained from $x \rightarrow x'$, with a fine metric on the space, the “length” of the connection should appear to contract.

Definition 2.2 A *θ -calculus* is any analytic structure which admits at least one real-valued time dimension.

Definition 2.2b A *θ -calculus* is an analytically typed category which witnesses at least one short trip from time to θ .

Equivalently, we let

$$p = \log_k(x) \lim_{0 \rightarrow k} p = \theta$$

hold for any measurable rod of an arbitrary length from some probabilistic center to a deviant locus. The retracts here are getting arbitrarily “shorter”, and closer to θ as some cardinal invariant approaches k . A functor acting by reflection, $\Sigma(k)$, produces a smaller and smaller co-factor as this function progresses through time.

Let $\mathcal{S}$ be a (real or complex) analytic space, and $\partial_H \vec{\mathcal{S}}$ its holomorphic exterior derivative. Let

$$k: \text{ext}(\mathcal{S}) \rightarrow \text{int}(\text{int}(\mathcal{S}))$$

be a Koszul connection. Then, there is a one-to-one set of cells between k -maps and Hurewicz isomorphisms of geometric forms. Let $\text{int}(\text{int}(\mathcal{S}))$ be totally real. Then, the set of Koszul connections becomes the set of Hermite conjugates. We have

$$K_i: \text{ext}(\mathfrak{S}) \rightarrow \text{int}(\text{int}(\mathcal{S}))^\dagger \simeq 0i$$

so that there is a fixed zero-object, which acts in a torsion-free manner across the transformation.

⁸ See [Con].

Proposition 2.2.1 Let $\mathcal{C}al(\theta)$ be a θ -calculus. Let K be a space in the n -category $\mathcal{C}al(\theta)$. Assume K is contractible. Then, K is *locally contractible* at θ .

Proof By the universal property of $\mathcal{C}al(\theta)$, there is always a Koszul connection to any constant section of the boundary of K to θ . If, for any point $\theta \in \partial K$, there is an obstruction to contraction, then there is a deviation to the trivial bundle ℓ .

Assuming the action on θ to be an obstruction-free lift from the boundary of K , we obtain that any neighborhood $\mathcal{U}(\theta)$ is contractible to θ . We can model this by

$$\Omega_{\theta}^G \xrightarrow{\phi} \Omega_{*}^G \star \ell;$$

Let $\mathfrak{r}$ be a representative of an analytic space. We reformat our claim by stating that there is an intersection

$$\mathfrak{r} \cap \ell = \text{QCoh}(\theta) = \mathfrak{p}$$

between any tangent slice of our K -space and the fiber base to which it is attached. Then, assuming ℓ is smooth, we invoke the property of Urysohn; for a *normal* topological space K , assuming each $\mathfrak{p}$ to be coherently differentiable, there is a short trip from $\mathfrak{p}$ to θ so that any contractible section of $\mathfrak{p}$ is contractible near θ .

So far, we have seen that “what it means” to be a K -space in $\mathcal{C}al(\theta)$ is that every connection over K is compactly generated by an n th-order derivative of θ . More concretely, K must be a geodesic space, and it must “locally resemble” some object in the category of topological spaces, and further must be injective into some groupoid. The K -space is then specified by the operad

$$\Omega_p^x \circ_{\partial k} G \circ \infty \text{Cats}$$

which gives us a precise coordinate, assuming K is decomposable into ruled spaces.

Remark Let $\mathfrak{c}$ be a cardinal invariant. Then, whence we integrate over a K -space to obtain its volume, we take

$$F = \int_k \text{sup}(\mathfrak{c} - n)$$

to be its *regular* (Urysohn) volume, with respect to a generic valuation given by adjoint functors in the category of modules. We define the distance function F by taking $\ln(f_i \in F)$ to be a logarithmic scalar, and for two elements f_i, f_j we define the relationship $f_i R f_j$ by saying that $j > i$ if j is “smaller” in the geometric sense, which makes it more productive as a divisor.

§3 Cardinal Invariants

Definition 3.0.1 A *cardinal invariant*, $\mathfrak{c}$ is a singlet category with at least one path from every co-category $\langle \mathfrak{c} \rangle$.

This is such a simple definition as to have given us a seemingly unlimited supply of power. Let us recapitulate.

Definition 3.0.1b A *cardinal invariant* is a final object of a subcategory which weakly models ZFC.

Theorem 3.0.2. For every irreducible polynomial p , there is a distinct cardinal invariant modeling $f(p)$.

The proof is forthcoming.

Example Let $\mathbf{10}$ be the first ten integers. Then we have $\text{sup}(\mathbf{10}) = \mathfrak{c}$. We have the series of chains:

Mod 1: $1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow 10$

Mod 2: $2 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow 10$

Mod 3: $3 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow <10$

...

$\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{10} \star k) = \text{Eq}(\mathfrak{c})$

Here, the right hand-side is the equivalence class *characterized by* an operator, k , and a cardinal invariant, in this case 10^1 . This has the flavor that we may blend it with any cardinal invariant with any (however weakly or strongly) defined set of properties we want. In order to make the most bang for our buck, we tend to try and make these invariants *really interesting*; that is, they will typically characterize some extremely important parameter that allows one some control over the mathematics involving them.

In our case, we let ε and $\partial\tau$ be our cardinal invariants. We define ε to be

$$\varepsilon = \lim_{x \rightarrow \theta} d(x, \theta)$$

and $\partial\tau$ is defined by

$$\partial\tau = \partial(d(x, \theta))^{-1}$$

For each segment of length $\partial\tau$, there is a “section” (with a retract) of the “trivial” fiber bundle

$$\mathcal{F} = \varepsilon(\partial K),$$

with the right-hand side a boundary-forming ε -chain for a K -manifold. That these are valid cardinal invariants follows from the fact that we can uniquely restrict ourselves, via the axiom of choice, to any of a set of functions $f(\varepsilon) \rightarrow \mathbf{S}$, where $\mathbf{S}$ is a closed interval.

§3.1.0 Rings as intervals

We will now resume from our earlier discussion on the loop group, $\text{LG}(d)$, of an object d . Firstly, this is now no longer an ordinary *mary sue* object – it is now a cardinal invariant. So, it has some

distinct properties. To start with, there is a defined “center” of $LG(d)$, $\mathfrak{F} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_k$, which is the arithmetic median.

Let $LG(d)_{EXT}$ be an extension of $LG(d)$. Then, one makes the appropriate adjustment to $\mathfrak{F}$ by the formula $\mathfrak{F}^k \circ \mathfrak{F}^1$. This is the shift functor on the arithmetic median. Many topological properties are determined by this shift. Most blatantly, the orientation of a torus is not preserved. However, parity is. This tells us that k is a normal *scalar* which parameterizes the set of “loopy” actions a group has. In the simple case, with a single loop suspended at a point, there is a correspondence between “rotations” of this loop, and “forcing notions” at the level of cardinal invariants. So, if one imposes the shift functor:

$$\mathbf{shift}: \mathfrak{F}^k \circ \mathfrak{F}^1 \simeq \mathfrak{o}(c) \Vdash c^\pm,$$

We see quite clearly that there is a ready-made isomorphism relating a strict arithmetic invariant with a rather flabby topological scenario. In such a case, we assume the boundary of the space $LG(d)$ acts upon is perfect, at least locally.

§3.1.1 Evaluation

The set of rotations of a curved space (e.g. an annulus), that is to say a space with a short trip to differentiable stacks, there is a direct link to the successor function on a tree-like graph.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ev}(U) &= \mathfrak{o}(U) \Vdash U^\pm \\ \text{ev}(\text{Hom}(U, X)) &= \mathfrak{o}(U, X) \Vdash \text{sup}(U, X)^\pm \end{aligned}$$

The *evaluation* function is herein stated so that for a display map between two compasses $U \rightarrow X$, the larger of the two will inherit the role as a sup-pole. This is a clear and obvious outcome one should expect when adopting a theory involving chains of invariants which are strictly decreasing with respect to some property.

$$\text{ev}(\text{Hom}(U, X)) = \partial\tau(\text{sup}(U, X) - \mathfrak{F})$$

Definition 3.1.2 As per [Filt, pg.4], we call the successor function $\text{ev}(\text{Hom}(P, K))^+$ the *Katětov ordering*.

Let $\mathbf{L} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ be a faithfully flat morphism, and $\mathbf{B}$ be convex. Then, assuming the underlying category to be a θ -calculus, for any >2 -ary chains in $\mathbf{B}$, there is a naturally defined *Katětov ordering*.

Definition 3.1.3 Let $A < B < C \dots < Y$ be an ordered list. Then, an element further from A or Y (formally, $\text{dist}(x, \{A, Y\})$) is said to be “more central.”

$$\text{dist}(x, \{A, Y\}) \propto \theta$$

Proposition 3.1.4 The most central element of any algebra with the Katětov ordering always has a left and right excision.

Proof: Because Katětov orderings are only guaranteed to exist for non-Boolean algebras, there are always at least three elements in a Katětov-ordered set. Therefore, there is always at least one *nexus*, or object admitting both left- and right-morphisms.

Now, we have a distinct cardinal invariant characterizing the “centrality” of an object, or the θ -like-ness of an accumulation point. We shall call this parameter, $\text{dist}(x, \{\inf(P), \sup(P)\})$ the *P-weight* of an object. Assuming that all subcategories of $\mathbf{P}$ admit short trips along diagonals means that the P-weight of an object corresponds roughly to its connectivity, as measured using these short trips. There is perhaps another appropriate way of stating this.

Proposition 3.1.5 P-weight measures the *centrality* of an element within a powerset.

Proof Because the number of connections are maximal on a more central element, we let the powerset $\mathbf{P}(P \cup n) \simeq \text{Hom}(P, P_n)$ be recorded as the total number of connections admitted by an interval.

Equivalently, a powerset is “more dense” than a set, and so members of multiple power sets should contribute the most to the density of a space. Thus, the P-weight encapsulates this density. P-weight is then a measure of the *number of relationships* between an object $q \in P$, and a topos $\mathbf{T}$.

Definition 3.2.0 Two objects, both in $\text{Hom}(X, Y)$, shall be called θ -differentiable if there is a *rule* R which relates these objects $\{x, y\}$ to θ , where θ is a unique cardinal invariant.

Note here that the Koszul connections are rank 1 isomorphisms. We call the portion of the diagram vertically below X, Y the *fan* of θ . We see that there is a 2-cell surjection from $(x \leftrightarrow y)$ onto the Koszul connections, so $\text{fib}(x) = \text{cofib}(y) = \text{Kosz}$. We see also that X and Y are not directly related to one another; they are instead transitively related through elemental inclusion. This elemental inclusion constitutes an “exit path” from the cardinal invariant to a coarse moduli space. x and y are both pullbacks for the cardinal invariant, and pushouts via opfibrations from one another.

$$\frac{xy}{xRy} \stackrel{\alpha}{=} \frac{xRy}{(Y \supset y)R^{-1}(X \supset x)}$$

In some sense, a space having a host of associated properties induces upon space-filling objects the properties of transport defined by said space. Every two pathwise connected points within subspaces have a transport structure determined by path-connected points at the *boundary* of the parent space.

§3.2.0 Ring extension

Let $\mathcal{R}$ be a ring and $\mathcal{R}[\mathfrak{o}^+]$ a near-identical ring with a positive scalar extension.

Definition 3.2.1 A *forcing notion* is a map $\text{sup}(\mathcal{R}) \rightarrow \mathfrak{o}^+$.

We write, for a forcing notion, $\mathfrak{o}^+ \Vdash (\mathcal{R}[\mathfrak{o}^+] \setminus \mathcal{R})$.

Definition 3.2.2 A *coherent forcing notion* is a forcing notion $\mathfrak{o}^+ \Vdash (B)$, where B is immersible in a regular ring spectrum.

Most of the forcing notions we have worked with so far have been coherent; however, it is actually easier, although less helpful, to give examples of *incoherent* forcing notions. Let

$$d\theta dt \rightarrow P_k$$

be a map from a space of unspecified P-weight to a space P_k . If P_k is unstable, then the notion

$$d\theta dt \Vdash P_k \setminus \theta$$

is incoherent, because $\text{QCoh}(P_k \setminus \theta)$ does not lie in the direct image of $\text{proj}(\text{ddt})$.

So, first off, we want our forcing notions to be coherent, at least in the sense that they are distributive over fibered products. This is why we often restrict ourselves to *rigid spaces* in 1-categories. A 1-cell $R \rightarrow R'$ between rigid spaces is *automatically coherent* if the centralizer of R exists and has at least one co-character. Every coherent forcing notion gives birth to at least one trivial extension of a ring by a urelement. These urelements are analogous to “hidden variables;” however, they are arithmetic. They are not “recorded” by the appropriate k-digital series of infinitesimals. Thus,

Proposition 3.2.3 Every pair of objects in a k-digital series is an ordered pair.

Proof Let $\{x,y\}$ be a 2-digital (binary) series. Then, we have x_y for the left-right reading and ${}_x y$ for the right-left reading. Thus, there is a reversible relationship xRy , and so they are comparable.

If we can accept that any two elements in a certain kind of pair are ordered, and allow that order to be by inclusion, then we can achieve very easily unobservable sets of digits beyond a certain place.

What is the *direct result* in translating from the geometric case to the cardinal invariant picture? Well, we observe that each “important” number is equally good a cardinal invariant as any other, depending on the necessity of the situation. So, writing

$$\int_0^1 p = 4\pi$$

gives us *just as much* information about an object as writing, say, “2.” In the Platonic sense, these are equally good approximations of some chosen ideal. It is only that the symbols of the formula are less

familiar to us than our natural numbers that they appear to require an additional layer of “convolution,” wizardry, know-how, or sophistication. This gives us a gameplay style which relies more heavily on its *symbolology* of that which is considered to be invariant than by providing invariant notions themselves. This should be a familiar approach to k-theorists and algebraic topologists, at least.

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